

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant. Part III. Solubilities of Some Electrolytes in Formamide at Different Temperatures

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Solubilities of over twenty electrolytes in formamide have been determined at different temperatures. These appear to be, in general, smaller than those in water. The temperature coefficients of solubility are also smaller than the corresponding values in water.

In connection with a research programme on the study of solutions in media of high dielectric constants, solubility data in formamide were needed, but literature revealed no such data. Although Colton and Brooker¹ determined solubilities of some electrolytes in formamide at 25°, the data were, however, found inadequate because the solubilities were given at one temperature only and the units used were *ing./litre* of saturated solution. On the other hand, solubilities in weight units were needed. It was therefore considered desirable to determine solubilities at different temperatures in weight units. This communication reports solubilities of twenty three different electrolytes in formamide at different temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL

Most of the electrolytes used were of A. R. grade. Some compounds, not available of A. R. quality, were purified suitably. The hydrated salts were heated to a constant weight to make them anhydrous. Formamide was redistilled under reduced pressure and was then stored in amber-coloured bottles until used.

Finely divided solute was added to a suitable quantity of formamide, contained in the solubility flask. The flask, in general, was heated to a temperature 10-15° higher than that at which the solubility was to be measured. The flask was shaken continuously to saturate the solution and then placed in a thermostat, regulated at a lower-desired temperature at which the solubility had to be determined. The solution was electrically stirred continuously with a glass stirrer for 4 to 5 hrs. and it was then allowed to stand for one hour or more, as necessary, for complete settling of the suspended solute. The clear supernatant liquid (3-5ml approx.) was withdrawn with the help of a pro-pipette, transferred to a weighed closed pyrex or silica dish, and was weighed again when the room temperature was attained. The dish was cooled in a dry-air enclosure and weighed on a balance, inside of which was kept dry with the help of P_2O_5 contained in an open dish. These precautions were necessary to reduce absorption of moisture by formamide to the minimum.

Two more such samples were taken at the same temperature of saturation at half-hour intervals and weighed as before. In order to obtain the amount of solute present, either of the following procedures was adopted according to convenience.

Evaporation Method.—The dish containing the weighed sample was heated carefully in an oven (it is necessary to clean the dish scrupulously before being used for sampling to avoid the creeping of the solute during evaporation process) and then on an electrical heater to expel formamide completely. Too rapid heating should be avoided otherwise formamide is charred and cannot be easily removed. The dish was cooled and weighed in a dry atmosphere, as described above. The process was repeated to obtain a constant weight. All the three samples taken were treated in a similar manner.

Precipitation Method.—In the case of halides and sulphates, the weighed sample was diluted with water and the anion content in the solution was determined gravimetrically. To test reliability of the procedure, a known amount of the substance under investigation was dissolved in formamide and then estimated gravimetrically. When the experimental and the theoretical values agreed within $\pm 0.5\%$, the procedure was applied to the samples of unknown solubility.

TABLE I

Uni-univalent electrolytes.

Solute.	Solubilities in g./100 g. of formamide at					
	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
NH ₄ Cl	11.02	11.20	11.71	12.06	12.41	12.70
NH ₄ Br	36.11	37.01	37.86	38.71	39.39	40.39
NH ₄ I	104.20	104.50	104.00	105.40	105.80	106.10
NaCl	9.32	9.05	8.91	8.71	8.55	8.42
NaBr	35.84	38.04	39.10	40.16	42.42	44.15
NaI	56.62	67.69	78.00	89.74	103.10	119.40
NaKCO ₃	40.46	41.39	42.20	43.22	44.38	45.42
KCl	6.30	6.34	6.41	6.49	6.56	6.69
KBr	21.38	21.67	21.73	21.93	22.07	22.19
KI	69.22	69.34	69.42	69.62	69.71	69.81
KNO ₃	15.55	16.71	17.61	18.06	20.30	21.59

DISCUSSION

The results obtained are summarised in Tables I and II. The values given are, in general, the mean of the results obtained with three different samples. In Table I the solubilities of some uni-univalent electrolytes and in Table II of others are recorded at different temperatures. These are expressed in g. solute/100 g. solvent and are correct within $\pm 1\%$.

Solubilities of different electrolytes in formamide are, in general, found to be less than the corresponding values in water. The temperature coefficient of solubility also appears to be, in general, smaller in formamide than that in water. This coefficient for sodium chloride is negative, contrary to that in water, indicating evolution of heat on solution.

TABLE II
Electrolytes other than uni-univalent.

Solute.	Solubilities in g./100 g. of formamide at							
	20°.	25°.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.	55°.
K ₂ SO ₄	0.336	0.34	0.348	0.35	0.356	0.357	0.358	
Na ₂ C ₂ O ₄	..	..	..	0.159	0.165	0.171	0.178	
BaCl ₂	11.76	12.470	13.120	13.950	14.820	15.420		
BaBr ₂	20.85	31.480	34.400	35.360	35.450	36.480		
CaCl ₂			22.890	23.580	24.530	25.890	27.180	
SrCl ₂	14.950	15.90	16.180	17.000	18.050	18.780	19.280	
SrBr ₂		19.05	21.260	23.400	26.320	28.500	32.150	
*PbCl ₂		5.623	6.134	6.390	6.893	7.413	7.873	
*PbBr ₂		12.02	14.820	18.290	23.280	27.320	30.180	
*Pb(NO ₃) ₂			153.700	155.200	158.900	160.300	162.800	164.800
MnCl ₂			5.888	6.663	7.017	7.849	8.216	9.555
MnSO ₄			1.758	1.845	2.012	2.092	2.181	

*More soluble in formamide than in water.

Halides, in general, follow the same pattern of behaviour as in water, i.e., iodide > bromide > chloride. Halides and nitrate of lead are more soluble in formamide than in water.

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